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A next generation Single Molecule Localization Microscope for multi-color imaging

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Abstract

A cutting edge single molecule localization microscope is presented. Single molecule localization microscopy, is an optical technique that allows localization of individual molecules such as proteins in their cellular context, with nanometer localization precision. Aberrations due to the optical elements in the microscope can decrease this localization precision. Therefore, for this new custom made super-resolution microscope, the light path was simulated with Zemax, in order to minimize the aberrations. With the knowledge gathered from the simulation the microscope path was designed and implemented.

Due to the flexibility of custom microscopes, we were able to develop a novel approach to perform multi-color with this microscope. This approach uses light that would be otherwise lost in a conventional single molecule localization experiment, to determine the color in multi-color experiments. A dual-color experiment showing the potential of this new approach is presented.

1. Introduction.

1.1. Single Molecule Localization Microscopy.

Fluorescence microscopy is an imaging technique widely used to study biological processes due to its ability to specifically detect labeled molecules. However there is an aspect that limits its power. This is the spatial resolution, which is a measure of the minimum distance at which two pointlike objects can be, so that we can still distinguish them. This resolution limit is due to the diffraction of light, and is given by the Abbe diffraction limit:

$$d = \frac{\lambda}{2 \cdot NA}$$

,where d spatial resolution, λ is the wavelength of light, and NA is the numerical aperture of our optical system. Single Molecule localization Microscopy (SMLM) overcomes the diffraction limit problem, allowing the detection of single molecules, with a resolution one order of magnitude under the diffraction limit. In contrast to other high resolution techniques like AFM or electron microscopy, SMLM benefits from labeling specificity of fluorescent microscopy.

A fluorophore can be approximated by a point source (Delta function), and due to diffraction, its image obtained by an optical system, is given by the point spread function (PSF). In the case of a wide field microscope this is an Airy function, that has a nonzero width. Therefore, when too many molecules are imaged at the same time, their PSF overlap (figure 1b). Consequently while in typical fluorescence microscopy fluorophores are imaged "all at once", SMLM relies on temporal decoupling of the emission of different fluorophore subsets, so that their PSFs do not overlap (1), (2), (3) (figure 1c.) Through fluorophore choice, appropriate sample preparation and laser excitation, a random and sparse fluorophore subset can be activated at each frame. Since their PSF do not overlap, a PSF model can be fitted to each molecule image in order to estimate their precise localization (4) (figure 1c).

For two dimensional (2D) imaging it is usual to take a two dimensional Gaussian as the PSF model (5) (figure 1f), to

approximate for the Airy function. The localization precision with which the x and y coordinates of the fluorophore can be estimated is:

$$\sigma \approx \frac{s}{\sqrt{N}}$$

,where N is the number of collected photons, and s is the spread of the PSF model (in the case of the Gaussian model, s is the standard deviation). According to this formula, while the diffraction limit is about 250 nm, the position of a fluorescent molecule, can be determined down to a precision of 10 nm with 600 photons.

As we have seen, the x and y position can be determined with high precision. In the case of trying to estimate also the z position of the fluorophore, the situation changes dramatically. For an aberration free optical system the 3D-PSF function is symmetric with respect to the focal plane, and its shape does not change much within the first 150 nm of z . This makes it quite difficult to precisely estimate the z position, and to tell if it is above or below the focal plane. To overcome this different approaches have been proposed. One of this approaches is to place a cylindrical lens in the beam path (6), introducing astigmatic aberrations in the PSF. The astigmatism produces an elongation of the single molecule image when it is out of focus. The elongation occurs along different axes, depending on whether the molecule is above or below the focal plane, and is bigger if the fluorophore is further away from the focal plane. By measuring the elongation, the distance to the focal plane of the fluorescent molecule can be estimated. In another approach, sophisticated optical design is used to perform PSF engineering (7).

Figure 1. (a) The schematic shows a subcellular structure (a microtubule network) that is uniformly labeled with specific fluorophores. (b) In conventional imaging, all of the fluorophores in the sample are simultaneously excited. Due to the resolution limit of fluorescence microscope, the resulting widefield image is poorly resolved and fails to reveal the underlying structure in the sample. (c) In localization based super-resolution microscopy, the imaging conditions facilitate activation of random subsets of fluorophores that are typically spatially well separated. These

fluorophores are then localized with sub-pixel precision and their coordinates are then used to create a super-resolution image of the sample. (d) The resulting super-resolution image provides fine structural information of the sample that is not accessible through a widefield image. (e) Comparison of a practical widefield image and a super-resolution image (In panel (e), the size bar is 2 μm . In all other panels, size bars are 300 nm) g) The pattern formed on a camera by a single fluorescent molecule is blurred by diffraction but can be fit by a model function to yield a localization with uncertainty at least an order of magnitude lower than the diffraction-limited resolution, depending on the detected photons. h) Ratiometric multi-colour imaging, makes use of two very close species and images them both in two channels simultaneously. i) In ratiometric multi-colour imaging, each localization event is identified in both channels and the ratio of the number of photons measured in each channel allows identifying the species. Figures (a)-(e) were taken from (8), f) from (9), g) and h) from (10).

In SMLM mainly three different methods are used for imaging. These are PALM (Photoactivation Localization Microscopy (1), (3)) STORM (Stochastic Optical Reconstruction Microscopy (2), (11)) and PAINT (Points Accumulation for Imaging in Nanoscale Topography (12)). STORM mostly uses fluorophores that can be stochastically turned on and off, which is usually achieved with organic dyes, and adequate buffer and illumination conditions. Organic dyes are able to emit thousands of photons. They are attached to the structures by a linker, which consists often on a pair of antibodies. This linker introduces a linkage error, which is normally about 10 nm. To prevent the organic dyes from photobleaching, oxygen scavengers systems are used in the buffer, and other buffer components are necessary to optimize the dye performances. The photochemistry of the organic dyes used in STORM allows them to enter long-lived dark states (tens of milliseconds to several hours in oxygen free environment), and then modulate their emission by returning only a small subset of them to the fluorescent state using low UV laser light. This long-lived states are different from bleaching, which is an irreversible process. The specific buffer conditions complicate multi-color, as the buffer may not be compatible with other fluorescent molecules. PALM normally utilizes fluorescent proteins (FP). Fluorescent proteins are genetically fused to the proteins of interest, and display low linkage error, because of their small size in comparison to antibodies. They also have higher labeling efficiency than organic dyes, as they will not get attached to other undesired structures. In PALM, a small subset of FP is randomly activated by using an activation laser. This subset is imaged and then bleached by the high power excitation laser. FP are less bright than organic dyes, and they emit about one order of magnitude less photons. PAINT labels are contained in the buffer, and randomly bind and unbind from the structure of interest. Upon binding of the label, a localization event can be observed. This can be done for example, using two complementary DNA strands, attached to the fluorescent molecule, and the structure to be detected (DNA-PAINT (13)). With this approach, the photon budget is infinite. However the unbound fluorescent molecules create a background while imaging.

1.2. Aberrations in SMLM.

Optical aberrations are wavefront deformations that occur during image formation and degrade the image quality. Aberrations within the microscope appear because of different reasons, such as imperfections in the manufacturing of the optical elements and imprecise alignment. However aberrations also arise from index mismatch between the sample and the immersion medium or due to sample inhomogeneities.

Aberrations can be classified into chromatic and monochromatic aberrations. Chromatic aberrations occur when different wavelengths are not focus on the same point. They can be axial or lateral chromatic aberrations, depending on whether they focus at different points along the optical axis, or transverse to it. Chromatic aberrations affect in particular experiments performed with more than one wavelength. Although lenses are specifically corrected to minimize chromatic aberrations, a certain amount is found in every microscope. Monochromatic aberrations are wavelength independent and can be easily approximated by Zernike polynomials. Among the different types of monochromatic aberrations, spherical aberrations, coma, astigmatism and defocus are highly relevant to microscopy. These aberrations degrade the PSF, breaking its axial (astigmatism, coma and spherical) or radial (coma and astigmatism) symmetry. Such degradations impact the accuracy and precision of the localization in SMLM. As previously reported, aberrations can not only reduce the peak intensity and localization precision of a molecule's PSF, but also affect the false positive and false negative rate. In the presence of coma, the localization error can reach up to 100 nm (14). The main reason for these errors is that in the presence of aberrations, radially and axially symmetric models do not approximate well enough the experimental PSF.

1.3. Multi-color Imaging.

Although single molecules can be localized with nanometer precision, this is sometimes not enough to understand their function, and it is necessary to study their change in distribution with respect to another structure. This can be done using fluorophores of distinct colors, and a proper combination of filters. Different methods can be used to obtain a multi-color

image with two different species.

By separating the fluorescent emission of the different species in time, one can do alternating or sequential imaging. In the former, the frames alternate between the two colors. In the latter, first one color is completely measured, before imaging the other one. In both cases, the images obtained for both colors need to be merged into a single image. This merging induces registration errors that are on the order of 10 nm (15). These methods also suffer from cross-talk. One particular example is the fact that organic dyes can undergo spontaneous activation, and emit when the other species is imaged.

However, instead of doing alternating or sequential imaging, the chromatically distinct fluorophores can be acquired simultaneously. Their emission can be split by a dichroic mirror. This separates the light by wavelength and the two species can then be imaged in different channels, either two cameras or two halves of the same chip. This is also susceptible registration to errors when combining the images of each channel, and to chromatic aberrations if the fluorophores emission spectra are far apart. To avoid these problems, an alternative is to use two fluorophores with close but slightly separated emission spectra, and again use a dichroic mirror to split them (16). This time, because the emission spectra overlap (figure 1g), both species appear in each channel, and the ratio between the intensity in the two channels can be used to determine the fluorophore species (figure 1h). This approach is called ratiometric dual-color imaging. To avoid registration errors when merging the images, only one of the channels can be used to reconstruct the final image. In particular, because of the close emission spectra, chromatic aberrations are minimal. However, since the light of the fluorescent molecules is split into two channels, and the final image based on one channel only, the localization precision is reduced. This can be crucial when imaging two fluorescent proteins, as their photon budget is limited.

Despite the efforts to improve multi-color imaging, in most cases the images remain of lower quality as compared to single-color ones. It is difficult to find compatible fluorescent molecules with similar photoswitching properties, exhibiting bright and fast blinking in the same conditions (laser light intensity, buffer).

1.4. Aim of this work.

In this work, I simulated a microscope using advanced optical software to minimize aberrations. I then built and aligned a cutting edge microscope, incorporating the knowledge gathered from the simulations. I demonstrated the performances of the microscope in terms of stability and imaging capacity. In particular, this microscope includes a novel approach to ratiometric dual-color imaging, for which I present a validation experiment.

2. Results and Discussion.

2.1. Simulations with OpticStudio.

2.1.1. Methodology. Simulations.

The simulations of the optical path of the microscope were performed with Zemax OpticStudio. Zemax OpticStudio is a software that allows designing, analyzing and simulating optical systems (17). Optics manufacturers often provide Zemax files for their consumers, helping them to simulate the components and assess the performances of their system.

For simulating optical systems in OpticStudio, one has to define the surfaces that make up the path, by providing different parameters such as materials, curvature radius and thickness of each surface. In our case, these surfaces are the different lenses in the beam path. In most cases, Zemax files for the lenses can be downloaded online and then placed at the desired plane in the system. The main tool to simulate optical systems within OpticStudio is a ray tracing tool. It simulates the trajectories of a grid of rays throughout the system using geometrical optics. The simulation results can be represented as a Spot Diagram (SD), which shows the intersection of the rays within the image plane (see figure 2 for example). In the case of a perfect optical system, all the rays going through the system will converge at the image plane on a single spot. Due to aberrations, this is not the case when simulating real systems. An other interesting tool to see the effects of aberrations are the aberration diagrams. This diagrams tells us which aberrations are introduced by each element of the system.

Although such a simulation does not take into account the diffraction of light, the SD can give a hint of which aberrations will

be present in the PSF. If the size of the SD is comparable to the size of the Airy disk, then the aberrations present in the SD will affect the PSF.

2.1.2. Simulations of the optical path with Zemax OpticStudio.

Since aberrations have a strong effect on the localization of molecules, simulating the microscope is a crucial step in the planning of a new optical system. To this end, the detection path of the microscope was simulated in order to select the lenses that introduce the least amount of aberrations. The illumination path does not need to be simulated, as the aberrations introduced by the lenses will not affect the shape of the PSF on the camera.

In SMLM, a pair of relay lenses is commonly used to obtain a longer beam path. In particular, this allows placing a dichroic mirror for dual-channel imaging, inserting at the conjugated plane to the BFP a phase mask to perform PSF engineering for 3D localization (7) or adaptive optics for aberration correction (18), (19). However, additional lenses introduce more aberrations. In order to evaluate the impact of relay lenses, we simulated two different setups for the detection path of the microscope, one with relay lenses and one without. In the former different lenses were compared to choose the least aberrating pair.

Zemax files for each lens could be downloaded from their respective providers, except for the objective. So the simulation had to be performed with an ideal objective. One should keep in mind however that the objective will be the main source of aberrations, due to the complex optics inside it. This could also be seen from simulations with a similar objective, for which we were able to get a Zemax file. But because objectives can contain different optics, we did not use this one for simulating our system. Therefore, we could only minimize the aberrations after the objective.

For the simulations two different wavelengths 680 nm and 700 nm were used. These are typical emission wavelengths of two organic dyes (Alexa647 and CF680) excited with a 640 nm laser. Four different points over our field of view are chosen to compute their SD. The field of view of the microscope is about $40 \times 40 \mu\text{m}$, so the points (0,0), (0,20), (40,0) and (-40,-40) were selected (all in μm).

The relay lenses were chosen to be a 250 mm and 200 mm focal length lenses. With them the magnification is 48, and without them it is 60. The pixel size we get with each magnification on a sCMOS camera (6.5 μm physical pixel size) are 135 nm and 108 nm. From simulations it is known that the optimal pixel size is around 100-150 nm (20).

For the simulations we started with pairThorLabs lenses, because they were the ones available in the lab. The simulation contained the ideal objective, the tube lens and the two ThorLabs lenses. The TL comes together with the objective, we therefore can not try out different TL. The SD of the simulations with ThorLabs lenses is shown in figure 2a. The aberrations introduced by this pair of relay lenses are shown in figure 2d. Then Zemax is used on this system to suggest the lenses from its stock catalog that reduce the SD of our system. With this tool I find out that the best option is to use a pair of Edmund lenses. The SD of the system with these lenses is shown in figure 2b. The aberrations introduced by these pair of relay lenses are shown in figure 2d. Finally a system without relay lenses is simulated (figure 2c). The aberrations of the TL, that is the only lens present in this system (the objective is ideal), are shown in figure 2d.

From the aberration diagram we can see that the ThorLabs lenses introduce much more astigmatism than the Edmund lenses or the TL. This is also seen in the elliptical form of the spot diagram (figure 2a). This astigmatism is the main difference between the Edmund and the ThorLabs pair of relay lenses, although coma is also about three times bigger for ThorLabs lenses. This can also be seen from the comet form of the SD (figure 2a, fields (40, 0) and (-40,-40)). On the other side, spherical aberrations are bigger for the Edmund lenses. Overall, the aberrations introduced by the Edmund lenses are a little bigger than the ones introduced by the TL, while the ones of the ThorLabs are much bigger.

Figure 2. Spot Diagrams and Seidel Diagrams of the different setups. The scale bar in the SD is 15 μm . Which is about the size of the Airy disk radius in each case. a) Set up with ideal objective, TL and ThorLabs relay lenses. b) with two Edmund lenses instead of two ThorLabs ones. c) only the objective and the TL. d) Aberration diagrams of the pairs of ThorLabs and Edmund lenses, and from the TL. Color represents the different types of aberrations introduced by each (From left two right: Spherical Aberration-Coma-Astigmatism-Field Curvature-Distortion-Axial chromatic aberration-Lateral chromatic aberration). The grid lines are separated 20 nm.

2.1.3. Discussion.

From the simulations it can be seen that the presence of two relay lenses strongly increases the size of the SD. It can be concluded from this that if not strictly needed, it is better not to use relay lenses. If necessary, Edmund lenses perform better than the ThorLabs ones for this system. However, while these simulations give as insights in what aberrations can be

present in our system, they do not include the object or the objective, which are the main source of aberrations in the optics.

One advantage of having the objective file would have been that instead of just selecting the lenses with less aberrations, one could have chosen lenses to compensated the aberrations introduced by the objective and the TL.

2.2. New super-resolution microscope.

2.2.1. Optical path.

The main body of the new microscope is shown in Figure 3a. The body houses a sample holder on an XY stage and the objective beneath it in a Z stage. In addition, several optical elements are present to illuminate the sample and collect the fluorescence.

The illumination lens focuses the laser on the back focal plane (BFP) of the objective. The objective then collimates the light on the sample, and after collects the fluorescent light. This light is then transmitted through the main dichroic, and reflected by the fluorescence dichroic. After this the TL generates an image on the camera. One or more filters are also need in front of the camera to block the lasers. The BFP lens can be introduced to look at the BFP of the objective. The cylindrical lens is introduced into the beam path to perform 3D imaging with astigmatism.

Figure 3. Microscope Body. a) SolidWorks lateral view of the microscope body. b) The setup of the main body of the microscope (BFP lens: back focal plane lens CL: cylindrical lens F: filter IR laser: infrared laser M: mirror QPD: quadrant photodiode TL: tube lens).

Apart from optics used to generate a fluorescent image, we also have a focus-maintaining system. This system is used compensate drift in z, in order to avoid losing the focus on the sample. It consists on a near infrared laser (785 nm), that is focused on the edge of the objective BFP. Because of this, it propagates from the objective with an angle sufficient to reflect in TIR (total internal reflection) on the coverslip, and come back on the opposite side of the BFP. Then the laser light is sent to a quadrant-photodiode (QPD). When the distance between the objective and the coverslip changes (as in the case of axial drift), the laser is displaced laterally on the QPD. Using an electronic feedback system between the objective stage and the QPD, the stage moves until the laser is centered on the QPD again, effectively correcting any axial drift.

Finally, a specificity of the microscope is the presence of three actuators oriented axially in the body. These piezoelectric actuators support a plate on which the objective is fixed. Their function is to bring the coverslip within range of the objective Z stage (which is limited to 100 μm) and to correct for any tilt of the coverslip, preventing coma aberrations, in particular with water-immersion objectives. The travel range of the actuators is 8 mm, and they can maintain their position with a precision of a few nanometers.

2.2.2. Methodology. Alignment of the microscope body.

In order to reduce aberrations, it is important to align each component of a microscope very precisely. The alignment of the microscope body on the optical table was performed using two perpendicular alignment lasers. The body was placed so that its axis went along two perpendicular lines of holes on the optical table. The alignment lasers followed those lines and therefore defined the optical axes. They were subsequently used to position the lenses and cameras.

Once the body aligned, the next step is to place the objective and the tube lens. While the position of the objective is fixed within the body (up to the movements of the objective piezo-stage), the tube lens needs to be aligned with respect to the objective itself. To this end, we placed a mirror above the objective, effectively allowing light from a distant object (in this case trees in the landscape) to be coupled in the objective. Since the objective has a very short working distance (3 mm), it forms the image of this distant object in its back-focal plane (BFP). In its correct position, the TL would send the object's image to infinity. In order to precisely align the tube lens, we made use of a system composed of an achromatic lens and a camera (infinite corrected camera). The lens was fixed on the camera so that it is located one focal length away from the camera chip. This alignment system was inserted along the optical axis. Thereon, when placing the TL after the objective, the correct position of the TL was found when an image of the distant object was formed on the camera. To center the TL the alignment laser was used, by ensuring that the direction of the laser was not changed when the TL was placed. After this, to position the main camera, the objective was removed, and the camera was placed so that the image of the distant object was focused on the camera.

2.2.3. Stability.

The stability of a single molecule localization microscope is crucial. Depending on the technique used (PALM/STORM/PAINT) or the abundance of the molecule of interest an experiment can take between 20 min and 5h in order to obtain a single image. Because of this long measurement times, the microscope needs to have minimum drift to not blur the structure of interest. There is no active system for the lateral directions, while the axial drift is compensated by the focus-maintaining system.

After localizing the molecules, cross-correlation can be used to estimate the lateral drift during the experiment and correct it. This is done by adding, for example, each 100 frames (with the localized molecules) into one image, and then using cross-correlation between the consecutive images. In addition, by adding a cylindrical lens, the molecules can be fitted in 3D and residual axial drift corrected. We performed a 3D experiment with fluorescent beads imaged with the 3D optics during 15 hours. It can be seen (figure 4a) that over the course of the experiment, the drift in the lateral directions was about 50 nm, which corresponds to a drift of about 3 nm/h, well within the typical localization precision and time scale. The drift in z is smaller, thanks to the focus-maintaining system. In figure 4b we see that the drift was about 16 nm over the 15 hours, which is 1 nm/h. Altogether, the microscope displays excellent stability.

Figure 4. Stability of the microscope. a) xy drift of the microscope over a period of time of about 15 hours (1 frame/min) b) z drift of over 15 hours.

2.2.4. Super-resolution experiments.

In order to show the capabilities of the microscope, we performed experiments with biological samples. We first imaged microtubules, which form filamentous structures in the cell. The molecules were imaged with DNA-PAINT, tagged with Atto655 dye. Figure 5a shows a diffraction limited image of microtubules in a cell. Using localization microscopy, we obtained a super-resolved image of the same microtubules (figure 5b), in which the improvement in resolution can be observed. These structures are about 25 nm in diameter, although when imaged with this technique they appear bigger due to linker size and localization precision (figure 5c).

In figure 5d an image of nuclear pores of two eukaryotic cell nuclei is shown. The nuclear pores are very important components of the nucleus, acting as gates for the molecules going in and out of the nucleus. This image was taken by detecting a protein from the nuclear pore complex (Nup96) with antibodies coupled with Alexa647 dye. There are 16 copies of this protein per nuclear pore complex, exhibiting an exceptional 8-fold symmetry (21). In figure 5e the ring distributions of the proteins can be observed. In the highlighted nuclear pore (figure 5g), one can appreciate the capacity of SMLM to decipher the eight fold symmetry of the nuclear pore complex. Figure 5f shows the profile across a nuclear pore. From this profile, the size of the ring structure can be estimated to be around 100 nm. This is in agreement with the 118 nm that were reported in the literature (22).

Figure 5. Single color images taken with the microscope. a) Diffraction limited image of microtubules. Scale bar is 10 microns. b) Microtubules imaged with DNA-PAINT, with Atto655. Scale bar is 10 microns. c) Profile across a microtubule (see yellow arrow in b). d) dSTORM image of nuclear porin Nup96 tagged with Alexa647. Scale bar is 1 micron. e) Zoom-in of the highlighted area in d). Scale bar is 1 micron. f) Profile plot across a nuclear pore. g) Zoom-in of a single nuclear pore of e).

2.2.5. Discussion.

In this section, a super-resolution microscope was presented. Custom microscopes have more flexibility than commercial ones. However, one also has to design and align them oneself, requiring expert knowledge. In addition, one also needs to setup the electronics and create an interface to make it accessible to a bigger range of scientists (both of which were out of the scope of this work). To give an idea of the complexity to deal with custom microscopes, in order to perform the experiments presented here, four different softwares were used to control the microscope.

The actuators are a new element that was not present in previous setups. The main idea is to use them to correct for small tilts of the coverslip, or tilts of the objective due to an imperfect manufacturing. This can be achieved due to the high precision of the actuators. The aforementioned tilting can induce aberrations, so correcting it can greatly improve the PSF shape, and thereon the quality of experiments. Improvement is still needed in the automation of the actuators. Indeed, at the moment they are controlled through a complex interface from the manufacturer, which limits the usability of the microscope for non-experts.

We have shown the good stability of the microscope, and its capabilities when performing 2D experiments. In addition, performing 3D experiments with it would be straightforward.

2.3. Novel ratiometric multi-color approach.

2.3.1. Optical path.

As mentioned previously, images taken in the ratiometric dual-color approach are of lower quality than for single color imaging. This is due to the loss of photons because of the splitting into two channels. The effect of photon loss is quite significant when using two FPs, because of the low photon numbers they emit.

Here, we developed a new approach for ratiometric dual-color imaging that does not require a splitting of the photons in the detection path. Instead, a second camera is used to collect the light reflected from the main dichroic (figure 6a scheme). Because the emission spectra of the fluorophores are quite broad, some of the fluorescence is not transmitted through the main dichroic (yellow and red dashed line in figure 6a plot). This light is lost in microscopes that use the conventional ratiometric approach. In this new approach, we 'recycle' this light and bring it on to a second camera. On this second camera, we will get more percentage of light of one of the fluorophores than from the other (see spectrums figure 6a plot). This second camera is then used to determine the fluorophore species of the fluorophores detected in the first camera.

Figure 6. Novel ratiometric approach. a) Simplified scheme of the approach b) Scheme of the illumination and the second camera setup, needed for this approach (F: filter L1-5: lenses M: mirror SM: single mode fiber).

The setup needed for performing such an experiment is seen in figure 6b. The main component is a tilted filter. This filter reflects the lasers, but transmits the fluorescent light that is reflected from the main dichroic (as seen in figure 6a plot). This can be achieved by taking advantage of a property of interference filters. These filters, so called thin-film filters, are made of many layers of different refractive index, and of thickness $\lambda/2$ (or a multiple of it), where λ is the wavelength transmitted through the filter. Some of the layers have semireflective coatings to reflect light back and forward between them. The transmission happens due to constructive interference of light reflecting between the different layers. However, when tilted their cut-off wavelength is shifted to lower wavelengths, as can be seen in figure 7a, for a 26° tilted filter.

As can be seen on in figure 6b, the single mode (SM) fiber is collimated by the L3 lens. This SM fiber comes from a laser box that contains four different lasers (405nm, 488nm, 561nm and 640nm). Then two lenses (L1 and L2) in a 4f configuration are used to bring the collimated laser (collimated by L3) to the microscope body, going over the tilted filter, and two mirrors that are used for precise alignment. The fluorescent light reflected from the main dichroic goes through the illumination lens (see figure 3b) and because of this it forms an image right before the tilted filter (figure 6b). This light is then transmitted through the tilted filter, and using two lenses (L4 and L5) the image is generated on the color camera (an EMCCD). These two lenses are also used to modify the magnification of this color detection camera, so that the pixel size (in nm per px) of the camera is similar to the pixel size of the main camera. A filter is placed in front of the camera to filter out residual laser light. In this case an EMCCD is used, because these cameras work better than sCMOS ones in low light conditions.

In order to be able to use the four different lasers without exchanging the tilted filter, a filter with four bands was chosen (446/523/600/677 Quadband filter). Its spectrum is shown in figure 7a. With the purpose of getting as much as possible of the reflected fluorescent light through the filter, the filter spectrum needs to be shifted very close to the laser wavelength, by tilting it. But one has to pay attention because when the spectrum gets near the laser emission, a difference of 1° can result in transmitting 2-3 orders of magnitude more of the laser through the filter. To avoid this, the transmittance of the filter for different angles was measured, for the four different wavelengths, and both polarizations (figure 7b). On the vertical axis the optical density (OD) of the filter is plotted, which is defined as $OD = -\log_{10}(T)$, where T is the transmittance.

Figure 7. Tilted 446/523/600/677 Quadband Filter a) The four different lasers, the spectrum of the filter for normal incidence (red), and for the 26° tilted filter (dark blue s-polarization, light blue p-polarization). This graphic was done with SearchLight Spectra Viewer of Semrock (23)). b) Optical density (OD) of the filter at different angles, for the four different lasers, and both polarizations. The OD is defined as $OD = -\log_{10}(T)$. Where T is the transmittance.

It can be seen from figure 7a how fast the OD drops for the 488nm, 561nm and 640nm wavelengths in the 26°-31° tilting range. For 26° all the colors are still over 4 of OD. We therefore chose to use this angle for the microscope setup. The fact that the OD of these three wavelengths drops almost at the same angle is important, because it means that the three respective bands of the filter are very close to the lasers for the same angle. By choosing this angle, we are collecting the most fluorescent light for the three wavelengths at the same time. This can be seen in figure 7a, where the spectrum of the 26° tilted filter is shown. Figure 7a plot was done with SearchLight Spectra Viewer of Semrock. This spectra viewer can be used to get an idea of how the filter spectra change when tilting the, but we observed by comparing with the experimental measurements, that it is not precise when looking at OD.

2.3.2. Methodology. Illumination and color camera.

During the alignment of the illumination, four lenses needed to be placed in 4f configuration before the objective; a configuration in which, within each pair of lenses, the lenses are separated by the sum of their focal length. To this end, we used a collimated laser. To place the illumination lens (inside the body) before the objective, the lens was moved along the optical axis until the laser came out collimated of the objective. To align L1, the objective was removed and the lens was placed so that the illumination lens collimated the laser. The same two-step procedure was repeated for L2 and L3. Finally the single mode (SM) fiber coupled to the laser combiner (laser box) was placed at the focal plane of the fourth lens. In order to center the lenses during the alignment, they were moved perpendicularly to the optical axis until the direction of the laser was unchanged by the presence of each lens. The filter was placed on a rotational mount and inserted between the illumination lens and L3, tilted at 26°.

L4 where placed using the infinite corrected camera, in the same way the TL was aligned in the previous section. L5 was

placed so that its focal plane was located at the color camera chip.

2.3.3. Super-resolution dual-color experiments.

In order to obtain a proof of principle using this new ratiometric approach, we imaged the nuclear pores of an eukaryotic cell nuclei tagged with two different fluorescent molecules. Nup96 was again labelled with Alexa647 using antibodies. The other tag was CF680 (another organic dye) that was attached to WGA proteins. WGA proteins are present in the cytoplasmic filaments of the nuclear pores, which are located inside the nuclear pore rings. The result is shown in figure 8a). Plotting the Ln of the number of photons in each camera of each localizations, we obtained figure 8b). This figure shows two close populations. The horizontal white line in figure 8b shows how the splitting between the two colors was done. The localizations below the horizontal line were assigned to Alexa647, and the ones above to CF680. The ones between the red lines were excluded.

Figure 8c) shows a zoom-in of the selected region in 8a. Figures 8d and e show the same region with only the localizations corresponding to one of the fluorescent dyes. In figure 8d the ring structure of Nup96 can be appreciated. While in 8e the central region of this rings can be seen. Cross-talk between the two dyes can be observed (yellow arrows) from the images: some localizations assigned to Alexa647 seem to be located inside the rings, and some assigned to CF680 appear to be part of the ring-like structures. This is due to the overlap of the two populations that can be observed from figure 8b, causing misassignments of the colors.

Figure 8. Super-resolution dual-color image. a) Overview of the nuclei. Nuclear pore proteins Nup96 and WGA are tagged with Alexa647 (red) and CF680 (blue). b) Ratiometric splitting plot. c) Zoom-in of selected region in a). d) Only Alexa647. e) Only CF680. In a the scale bar is $10\mu\text{m}$. In c)-e) it is $1\mu\text{m}$.

2.3.4. Discussion.

In this sections a novel approach for multicolor imaging has been presented. A proof of principle experiment of this new approach has be shown (figure 8). In theory, this approach could reach the precision of single color experiments with two colors, as the photons that reach the main camera are the same that would reach it in a single color experiment.

One disadvantage of this new approach is that the whole illumination setup is aligned for a given angle of the filter. If a new filter is to be used at a different angle, the entire illuminations path needs to be realigned. Because of this, a better choice is a filter that at a given angle, has a spectrum band close to each of three excitation wavelengths (488nm, 561nm and 640nm). In the future, a multi-mode (MM) fiber will be implemented, for performing homogeneous illumination over the field

of view (24). This will be done by placing a flip mirror, to be able to change between the epi or TIRF illumination of the SM fiber, to the homogeneous illumination of the MM fiber.

In the experiment shown in figure 8, two organic dyes were imaged in a two-color experiment. As fluorescent proteins are very dim, two-color experiments are not usually performed in the conventional ratiometric approach due to the loss of photons when splitting the light into two channels. However, this novel approach without splitting could be further applied to two FPs. FPs have advantages with respect to organic dyes and antibodies. They have a higher specificity, much lower linkage error and are less dependent on special buffers. In addition, they can be genetically added to most proteins. Furthermore, currently, a problem for dual-color experiments is that the buffer from Alexa647 deteriorates rapidly over time, reducing the blinking and quality of images over time. Therefore the number of experiments that can be performed is limited, reducing the amount of data that can be taken per sample. FPs do not require such buffers, therefore using our approach with two FPs larger imaging times than currently would be possible, and so larger amount of data could be gathered. Our new approach could therefore enable imaging with two FPs, allowing longer imaging times and higher quality two-color images.

In addition, the optical setup can be further optimized. For instance, a current issue is the background on the color camera. To prevent reflections of the laser from reaching the cameras, the beam path needs to be encased in a box. However, most background is not laser reflections, but laser transmitted by the tilted filter. For this, using a clean up filter to narrow the laser emission may be helpful to improve the signal to noise ratio. Depending on the experiment, a different main dichroic may perform better, so different dichroic could be tried out. Finally, in our setup we opted for a filter that covers all the wavelengths, however single band filters could be also tried out to optimize for specific pairs of dyes or FPs.

The current analysis of the data can also be improved. At the moment, data on both cameras are fitted with a Gaussian model to estimate the intensity of the localizations on each camera. The estimated intensities are then used for color assignment. However, this Gaussian fit is not very accurate at determining intensities. Fitting the data with an experimental PSF (25), instead of using a Gaussian would improve the photon count estimation.

3. Conclusions.

In this work the setup for a new custom single molecule localization microscope has been shown. The microscope beam path was simulated with a high performance optical simulation software. From the simulations it was shown that if not necessary, it is better not to include relay lenses in the setup. In addition, a novel approach for ratiometric dual-color approach was implemented. This new approach does not rely on splitting of the light before the main camera. Instead it uses light that is normally lost in conventional setups and brings it on a second camera. This "recycled" light is then used to determine the color of the different fluorophores that were imaged on the main camera. The advantages of this method with over the conventional ratiometric approach, suggest that it can improve the quality of dual color imaging, and may be used for imaging two FPs at a time.

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Supplements

Table of microscope components

Component	Name / Description	Manufacturer
Objective	APON 60 x OTIRF 1.49 NA oil immersion objective	Olympus
Tube lens (TL)	SWTLU - C 180 mm tube lens	Olympus
Illumination lens	1 inch 150 mm focal length achromat	ThorLabs
L1 and L2	2 inch 250 mm acromats	ThorLabs
L3	1 inch 50 mm achromat	ThorLabs
L4	1 inch 200 mm achromat	ThorLabs
L5	1 inch 500 mm achromat	ThorLabs
Mirrors	2 inch dielectric mirrors on kinematic mount	ThorLabs
BFP lens	50 mm achromat	ThorLabs
Tilted filter	446 / 523 / 600 / 677 Quadband Filter	AHF
Main dichroic	TIRF Quand Line Beamsplitter zt405 / 488 / 561 / 640 rps	AHF
Fluorescence dichroic	SP beam splitter T750PXRXT	AHF
Filter color camera	700 / 100 (used for the Alexa 647 experiments)	AHF
Filter main camera	667 / 37 (used for the Alexa 647 experiments)	AHF
Color camera	EMCCD evolve512	Photometrix
Main camera	sCMOS Orca Flash 4.0	Hamamatsu
Focus - maintaining system laser	iBeam Smart 785 nm	Toptica
Laser box	iChrome MLE	Toptica
Quadrant photodiode (QPD)	SD197 - 23 - 21 - 041	Laser components
Actuators	N - 472 PiezoMike Linear Actuator	PI
Z - stage	P - 726	PI
XY stage	HCU - 3 D	SmarAct
Cylindrical lens	1 m focal length cylindrical lens	.